

Non-Conditional Anatomically-Accurate 2D Synthetic Mask Generation

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Abstract

Although the use of AI models in medicine reveals great potential, the use of medical images for the training of models understandingly raises ethical and privacy concerns. This study aims to implement a WGAN-GP model that uses a set of lung CT scans for cancer-suffering patients to generate accurate 2D synthetic semantic segmentation masks, by segmenting each CT scan into semantic masks. To compare model's performance, different sample resolutions and hyperparameters were experimented with. Results obtained demonstrate the model's capability to correctly map lung anatomy and segment its different components, thus producing realistic and feasible semantic segmentation masks. While current findings are limited to 2D and sensitive to sample resolution, prospects envision branching out into more complex 3D medical-grade samples. Said results highlight the potential for such architectures to be used in tandem with mask-conditioned generative models and two-step data augmentation.

Keywords: Generative AI ; Deep Learning ; Mask Synthesis ; Synthetic Semantic Segmentation ; Lung Cancer

1 Introduction

Lung cancer remains one of the leading causes of cancer-related mortality worldwide. Early detection is crucial for improving survival rates, as treatment options are far more effective when the disease is identified at an initial stage. Medical imaging techniques, particularly computed tomography (CT), play a central role in this process, as they enable clinicians to detect pulmonary nodules that may indicate the onset of lung cancer. However, interpreting CT scans is not trivial: radiologists must carefully differentiate between malignant nodules, benign structures, and imaging artifacts, a task that is both time-consuming and prone to inter-observer variability. The present work serves purely as a preliminary work and as a proof of concept demonstrating that, in the near future, a similar GAN-based model could potentially achieve this type of results when generating masks in more complex environments, such as in a three dimensional space or in a conditional, patient-specific mask generation. Despite being in the early stages, this work demonstrates that the WGAN-GP model can generate masks that play a significant role in data augmentation and patient-specific, controlled data enhancement, marking a potential breakthrough in the field of medical imaging. The primary objective of this study is to develop a model that can generate anatomically-accurate 2D masks which highlight the desired anatomical components. The code related to this work is publicly available in a GitHub repository¹.

2 Methodology

2.1 Dataset

The Lung Image Database Consortium image collection (LIDC-IDRI) [1] consists of diagnostic and lung cancer screening thoracic computed tomography (CT) scans with marked-up annotated lesions. This dataset is composed of several axial CT scans collected from patients diagnosed with lung cancer. Only scans containing visible nodules were selected in order to focus on clinically relevant regions. The lung parenchyma and nodules were segmented independently using the segmentation model suggested by [4], and their respective masks stored.

During training, these masks were combined into a single 3-channel representation: background, lung, and nodule. Each channel was one-hot encoded as a binary map, producing a structured, multi-class representation of the CT scans. The following figure shows a CT scan and the respective combined mask, following the logic explained before.

Figure 1: Example of a random thoracic CT scan mapped into a combined mask, highlighting background (black), lung (blue), and nodule (white).

2.2 Experimental Protocol

Initially, DCGAN [3] was implemented, however its simplistic architecture led to unsatisfactory results. So, we developed a WGAN-GP [2] tailored for multi-class mask image synthesis in medical imaging tasks. The generator creates multi-channel mask images, each representing a semantic class, by gradually upsampling a latent vector using transposed convolutional layers with instance normalization and ReLU activations. In order to produce a scalar score for realism, the critic discriminator downsamples input images using convolutional layers with instance normalization and LeakyReLU activations.

The critic is optimized to maximize the Wasserstein distance between real and fake samples, with a gradient penalty enforcing the 1-Lipschitz constraint. Furthermore, to improve anatomical plausibility, we add a **mask regularization term** that motivates the generator to produce confident, one-hot-like semantic masks. A **channel-balanced pixel-wise loss** (Eq. 3) was implemented in order to mitigate inter-channel imbalance (background, lung, nodule). This balanced pixel-level loss consists of a Binary Cross Entropy between generated and ground-truth masks, weighted per channel. Also, Instance Normalization was chosen instead of Batch Normalization to achieve higher-resolution mask synthesis in WGAN-GP, improving overall training stability and sample quality.

Finally, a thorough experimental evaluation of both models (the Balanced Loss WGAN-GP and the standard WGAN-GP) was conducted to determine their relative performance and efficacy. The hyperparameters used in the training process are listed at the top of the next page.

2.3 Performance Evaluation

In order to evaluate the performance of the developed models, we computed the Wasserstein Loss (Eq. 1) and the Gradient Penalty (Eq. 2) for both WGAN-GP variants, to show how these values reflect the adversarial training stability and discriminator's capability of solving for the Wasserstein distance. For the Balanced WGAN-GP, we also monitored the Balanced Pixel Loss (Eq. 3), which is designed to capture the anatomic relevance of generated samples. Taken together these measures enabled an assessment of the convergence and training dynamics of the

¹<https://github.com/damaral31/INESCTEC-project>

Table 1: Model Hyperparameter Configuration

models	balanced_weights	latent_dim	num_classes	ngf	ndf	lambda_gp	lambda_reg	optimizer_G	optimizer_D	g_train	d_train	epochs
WGAN-GP	None	100	3	64	64	10	0.1	lr=2e-4, betas=(0.5, 0.999)	lr=1e-4, betas=(0.5, 0.999)	2	1	500-1000
Balanced WGAN-GP	[0.5, 1.0, 3.0]	100	3	64	64	10	0.1	lr=2e-4, betas=(0.5, 0.999)	lr=1e-4, betas=(0.5, 0.999)	2	1	500-1000

different approaches. The corresponding loss functions are defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_W = E_{\mathbf{x} \sim P_r} [D(\mathbf{x})] - E_{\tilde{\mathbf{x}} \sim P_g} [D(\tilde{\mathbf{x}})] \quad (1)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{GP} = \lambda E_{\tilde{\mathbf{x}} \sim P_g} \left[\left(\|\nabla_{\tilde{\mathbf{x}}} D(\tilde{\mathbf{x}})\|_2 - 1 \right)^2 \right] \quad (2)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{pixel} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{c=1}^C w_c \text{BCEWithLogits}(x_{i,c}^{gen}, x_{i,c}^{real}), \quad (3)$$

where w_c are class-specific weights for background, lung, nodule. Taken this case, the final generator loss is then given by the sum of the adversarial loss between the Generator and Discriminator and the Balanced Pixel Loss (Eq. 3), where λ controls the trade-off between adversarial training and pixel-level fidelity.

3 Results

A simple DCGAN was previously implemented, but due to its limited architecture, it failed to produce meaningful results. Therefore, the following results correspond to the training of both the standard WGAN-GP and the Balanced WGAN-GP. In these experiments, the classes were mapped to colors as follows: background (red), lung (green), and nodule (blue).

Figure 2: Side-to-side 64×64 masks generated by a DCGAN, a WGAN-GP and a Balanced WGAN-GP, respectively.

Figure 3: Side-to-side 64×64 masks generated by a WGAN-GP and a Balanced WGAN-GP, respectively.

Figure 4: Side-to-side 128×128 masks generated by a WGAN-GP and a Balanced WGAN-GP, respectively.

As shown in Figure 2, DCGAN was not able to capture any meaningful visual patterns. Furthermore, overall the Balanced WGAN-GP performed better when learning and reproducing the anatomical structures, as illustrated in Figures 3, 4, and 5, revealing cleaner images and nodules inside lungs more often (Fig.4). At lower resolutions (Figures 3 and 4), the models produced generations with higher variability and greater sample diversity, indicating that the training dynamics were more stable and less exposed to a local minimum. However, when the resolution was increased to 512×512 (Figure 5), both WGAN-GP models showed clear

Figure 5: Side-to-side 512×512 masks generated by a WGAN-GP and a Balanced WGAN-GP, respectively.

evidence of mode collapse [5], as illustrated in Figure 6, with outputs becoming increasingly homogeneous across the last hundred epochs.

Figure 6: 512×512 Balanced WGAN-GP results across the last 100 epochs.

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, and as shown before, the implementation of the Balanced Pixel Loss (Eq. 3) revealed significant gains in generating samples with more variety and details, thus creating more anatomic-accurate lung and nodule masks. Also, in higher resolutions this models approximate mode collapse in higher resolutions: this ensures that data must have more variability. Results are looking promising, however higher resolutions need further methodological developments in order to avoid mode collapse, either by using a deeper architecture or revamping the training script.

In future work, it is clear that an addition of semantic segmentation components (such as other relevant anatomic structures - for example, the bone) is needed in order to further guide the generative process. Furthermore, this process will be expanded into conditional, patient-specific mask generation and mask-conditioned generative AI models will be trained for result validation and true data augmentation.

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